

RELEVANCE OF THE PROBLEM OF CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA IN OBSTETRICS

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Abstract. The problem of undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia is currently very relevant due to its high prevalence (the frequency of its individual manifestations ranges from 26 to 80% according to different authors) [2, 3, 6], as well as the clinical polymorphism of this pathology. This sample was divided into 2 groups: Group 1 – 100 patients aged 15 to 30 years with such manifestations of undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia, such as myopia, mitral valve prolapses, varicose veins of the lower extremities, group 2 – 50 patients aged 15 to 30 years without signs of this defect. According to the results obtained, the predominant sign of connective tissue defect in group 1 of this sample is myopia of varying degrees – 58%, while the frequency of varicose veins of the lower extremities and mitral valve prolapse is 30% and 12%, respectively. Among myopic visual impairments, mild (58%), moderate (26%) and high (16%) were predominant. Thus, based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the course of pregnancy and childbirth in patients with undifferentiated forms of connective tissue dysplasia in the form of varying degrees of myopia, varicose veins of the lower extremities and mitral valve prolapse is accompanied by a high incidence of obstetric and perinatal complications.

Key words: Pregnancy, non-differential connective tissue dysplasia, complication, fetal hypoxia.

Actuality. The problem of connective tissue defect in undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia implies visceral changes of varying severity, entailing serious consequences, which determines the spread of this pathology in many areas of medicine. Thus, in recent years, this defect has also become an object of attention in obstetric practice, due to the fact that undifferentiated dysplasia of the connective tissue can have an adverse effect on the course of pregnancy, childbirth, perinatal morbidity and mortality of newborns. Thus, pregnancy pathology is significantly more common in women with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia than in healthy women – from 85.5% to 53.3% [4]. In addition, there is a high risk of placental insufficiency, untimely passage of amniotic fluid [5], prolapse and prolapse of the internal genitalia [8]. At the same time, given the phenotypic polymorphism of this pathology and the great interest of researchers in this problem, there is no generally accepted information on the features of the course of pregnancy, childbirth and outcomes in women with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia. A number of authors point to a high incidence of complications, while others do not note a similar pattern in this pathology.

Purpose of the study. The aim of the work is to study the features of the course of childbirth, to identify obstetric and perinatal complications in women with such manifestations of undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia as myopia, mitral valve prolapse, varicose veins of the lower extremities, as well as to establish the relationship between the occurrence of obstetric and perinatal complications and the presence of this defect in a woman.

Material and methods of research. According to the goals, the study included 150 patients who were under observation and gave birth at the Perinatal Center of the Healthcare

Institution of the Ural Region "1st Republican Clinical Hospital of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan" in 2023. This sample was divided into 2 groups: group 1 – 100 patients aged 15 to 30 years with such manifestations of undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia as myopia, mitral valve prolapses, varicose veins of the lower extremities, group 2 – 50 patients aged 15 to 30 years without signs of this defect.

The study assessed the sum of reported cases of obstetric and perinatal complications with suspected manifestations of undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia in this sample, followed by the calculation of the mean score for each complication.

Results of the study. According to the results obtained, the predominant sign of connective tissue defect in group 1 of this sample is myopia of varying degrees – 58%, while the frequency of varicose veins of the lower extremities and mitral valve prolapse is 30% and 12%, respectively. Among myopic visual impairments, mild (58%), moderate (26%) and high (16%) were predominant.

In women with undifferentiated forms of connective tissue dysplasia, there is a high incidence of obstetric and perinatal complications, in the form of preeclampsia (12%), premature rupture of amniotic fluid (14%), weakness of labor (20%), threat of scar failure on the uterus (4%), threat of premature birth (4%), rapid labor (2%), divergence of perineal sutures (2%), intrauterine fetal hypoxia (32%), fetal growth retardation (7%), chronic placental insufficiency (2%) and umbilical cord entanglement (6%). Already in the first pregnancy, women in this group have a high risk of complications, the most common of which are weakness of labor (16%) and intrauterine fetal hypoxia (3.4%). Thus, the leading complications of pregnancy and childbirth identified in group 1 are intrauterine fetal hypoxia and weakness of labor.

In addition, a low-birth fetus with signs of intrauterine hypoxia was observed in group 1 women more than 5 times more often than in the group of women without undifferentiated forms of connective tissue dysplasia. (32% and 6%, respectively).

The obstetric anamnesis of group 1 women was more than 4 times complicated by fetal loss syndrome in early and late pregnancy. Prior to the analyzed pregnancy, the patients of this group had a non-developing pregnancy in 1.8% of cases and antenatal fetal death in 1.3% of cases, while the patients of the 2nd group without undifferentiated forms of connective tissue dysplasia did not have the above-mentioned pregnancy complications. Group 1 women were 1.5 times more likely to have a history of spontaneous abortions (12.2%). In women without undifferentiated forms of connective tissue dysplasia, there were no spontaneous abortions before the analyzed pregnancy.

Findings. Thus, based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the course of pregnancy and childbirth in patients with undifferentiated forms of connective tissue dysplasia in the form of varying degrees of myopia, varicose veins of the lower extremities and mitral valve prolapse is accompanied by a high incidence of obstetric and perinatal complications. Analysis of the results obtained indicates the existence of a direct pattern between the presence of a connective tissue defect and the development of complications of pregnancy and childbirth in these women.

References:

1. Викторова И.А. Методология курации пациентов с дисплазией соединительной ткани семейным врачом в аспекте профилактики ранней и внезапной смерти: дис. ... д-ра мед. наук. Ставрополь, 2004. 406 с.
2. Земцовский Э.В. Соединительнотканые дисплазии сердца. СПб.: ТОО «Политекс-Норд-Вест», 2000. 115 с.
3. Кадурина Т.И. Наследственные коллагенопатии. Клиника, диагностика, лечение, диспансеризация. СПб., 2000. 270 с
4. Кильдиярова Р. Р., Нечаева Г. И., Чернышова Т. Е. Дисплазия соединительной ткани //ББК 57.3 А-77. – 2020.
5. Мирзаев О. В., Шодикулова Г. З., Фозилова М. РАСПРОСТРАНЁННОСТЬ НЕДИФФЕРЕНЦИРОВАННОЙ ДИСПЛАЗИИ СОЕДИНИТЕЛЬНОЙ ТКАНИ У ПОДРОСТКОВ САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ //VOLGAMEDSCIENCE. – 2021. – С. 158-160.
6. Силаева Н. В., Ляшенко А. С., Ляшенко Е. Н. Недифференцированная дисплазия соединительной ткани и беременность //Modern Science. – 2021. – №. 5-2. – С. 69-73.
7. Уринова Р. Ш. и др. Роль недифференцированной дисплазии соединительной ткани в развитии пролапса гениталий у женщин репродуктивного возраста. – 2022.
8. Юнусова З. М., Шавази Н. Н. БЕРЕМЕННОСТЬ И ПЕРИНАТАЛЬНЫЕ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЯ У ЖЕНЩИН С ОЖИРЕНИЕМ //JOURNAL OF REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AND URO-NEPHROLOGY RESEARCH. – С. 42.
9. Avanisyan V. et al. Morphology of facial skeleton in children with undifferentiated connective tissue dysplasia //Archiv EuroMedica. – 2020. – Т. 10. – №. 3. – С. 130.
10. Dildora K., Zikiryaevna G., Zarnigor Y. PREGNANCY AND UNDIFFERENTIATED CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 6. – С. 1228-1232.
11. Khudoyarova D. R., Kobilova Z. A., Shopulotov S. A. OPPORTUNITIES INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHOD-GAMIFICATION //Онтологические и социокультурные основания альтернативного проекта глобализации. – 2021. – С. 361-364.
12. Khudoyarova D., Tursunov N., Shopulotova Z. DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS FOR SYMPTOMS OF ACUTE ABDOMEN IN WOMEN AT THE CURRENT LEVEL //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 757-760.
13. Khudoyarova D., Yusupov O., Shopulotova Z. ANEMIA IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH VARICOSE DISEASE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 761-765.
14. Khudoyarova D. R. et al. IMPROVEMENT OF METHODS OF NATURAL FERTILITY RESTORATION IN WOMEN WITH INFERTILITY CAUSED BY ENDOMETRIOSIS //Известия ГГТУ. Медицина, фармация. – 2020. – №. 4. – С. 20-22.
15. Khudoyarova D., Tuxtaulova Y., Kudratova S. WAYS TO PREVENT POST-ABORTION COMPLICATIONS //Бюллетень студентов нового Узбекистана. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 99-102.
16. KHUDOYAROVA D. R. et al. ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF WOMEN'S LIFE OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE WITH SURGICAL MENOPAUSE //БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ

ЖУРНАЛИ. – 2020. – С. 48.

17. Rubio J., Kytтарыs V. C. Undifferentiated Connective Tissue Disease: Comprehensive Review //Current Rheumatology Reports. – 2023. – Т. 25. – №. 5. – С. 98-106.

18. Nuralievna S. N., Maqsadovna Y. Z. Ortiqcha vazni bor ayollarda homiladorlik va tug'ruqning kechishi va asoratlari //Ta'lim fidoyilari. – 2022. – Т. 22. – №. 7. – С. 429-438.

19. Nuralievna S. N., Maqsadovna Y. Z. PREGNANCY AND CHILDBIRTH COMPLICATIONS IN OVERWEIGHT WOMEN.

20. Shavkatovna S. G., Rakhimovna K. D., Khudoyarova D. R. STUDY AND TREATMENT OF THE ORIGINS OF OBESITY IN PREGNANT WOMEN //Next Scientists Conferences. – 2022. – С. 46-51.

21. Shopulotova Z. A., Khudoyarova D. R., Solieva Z. M. PREGNANT WOMEN WITH PYELONEPHRITIS //American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2023. – Т. 15. – С. 268-271.